

ISOTENSOID PRESSURE VESSELS BASED ON NON-GEODESIC ROVING TRAJECTORIES

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SUMMARY: In this paper we evaluate the effect the application of non-geodesic trajectories has on the geometry and performance of composite pressure vessels. This evaluation is based on two cases: firstly we apply non-geodesic trajectories on a meridian profile that is determined according to geodesics and explore the consequences of this application for the mechanical performance while assessing the obtained flexibility for the minimum and maximum vessel radius. Secondly, with the aid of maximum-friction-utilising non-geodesics, we derive the optimal meridian shape providing equal fibre forces at every place belonging to the vessel. While having slightly enlarged design possibilities, the principle of isotensoid fibre loading is here still valid.

KEYWORDS: Composite pressure vessels, Isotensoids, Non-geodesic trajectories, Friction

INTRODUCTION

Compared to their steel counterparts, composite pressure vessels can be characterised by several qualities: significantly reduced weight, less sensitivity to environmental influences, in some cases, better impact resistance and increased safety [1]. A key factor in their design and development process is the creation of equally tensioned roving paths that are mainly based on the principle of geodesic winding [3, 4, 6, 8]. With the term geodesic we refer here to curves representing the shortest paths connecting two arbitrary points on a continuous surface [2,7].

Despite the fact that geodesic trajectories do maximally reduce the associated weight, their geometry combined with the requirements on the vessel for static equilibrium satisfaction is certainly limiting the available design space [3, 4]. A typical example of this restriction is the limit for the minimum radius a particular vessel can obtain. As known from the literature, the reinforcing layer on a rotationally symmetric mandrel can, in the vicinity of the polar opening, not be in equilibrium with the internal pressure and the eventual external forces. In addition, the ratio of the minimum and maximum radius is in general subjected to particular restrictions.

In this paper we outline a simplified design procedure for isotensoids that are based on non-geodesic roving trajectories. In the first section we briefly present the theory for the determination of non-geodesic trajectories on shells of revolution, and accordingly derive some simplified expressions for that purpose. In the next section, the evaluation of the basic equilibrium equations that govern the design of isotensoid pressure vessels is briefly outlined. The shapes of such vessels are based on application on geodesic paths and will here be referred to as “classical isotensoids”. Application of non-geodesic trajectories on classical

isotensoids however, is indeed able to enlarge the design space (especially in terms of polar opening radius variation). The associated variation in fibre force is in the order of the friction coefficient itself. In the subsequent section we outline the determination of the optimal meridian profile that is based on non-geodesics. This procedure requires a combined evaluation of the governing equations for the shape and the differential equations describing non-geodesic trajectories. While providing some flexibility for the dimensioning of the minimum and maximum vessel radius, the fibres are equally loaded at every position on the mandrel. In the last section of the main part, we demonstrate some differences related to non-geodesically overwound “classical isotensoids” and maximum-friction-based non-geodesic meridian profiles. Finally, some conclusions and recommendations are given.

NON-GEODESIC TRAJECTORIES

Curvatures

We consider here an elementary piece of a convex surface being part of a shell of revolution. Typically, the fibre path placed on the presented surface element is generally characterised by two radii of curvature (figure 1): the normal one R_n , (perpendicular to the surface element), and the so-called geodesic curvature, (located in-plane of that surface). The fibre is subjected to a longitudinal force F , a normal force per unit length f_n and a lateral force per unit length f_μ . The static equilibrium of the forces in the direction perpendicular to the surface can be expressed as follows:

$$f_n R_n \Delta\varphi = 2F \sin\left(\frac{\Delta\varphi}{2}\right) \approx F\Delta\varphi \Rightarrow f_n = \frac{F}{R_n} \quad (1)$$

The same reasoning applies on the equilibrium of the lateral forces:

$$f_\mu R_g \Delta\omega = 2F \sin\left(\frac{\Delta\omega}{2}\right) \approx F\Delta\omega \Rightarrow f_\mu = \frac{F}{R_g} \quad (2)$$

The lateral fibre force is generated by friction that is situated between the placed fibre bundle and the supporting surface. The condition for fibre placement stability is [5, 9, 10]:

Fig. 1: Normal and geodesic radii of curvature describing a curved fibre path

$$\mu \geq \left| \frac{f_\mu}{f_n} \right| = \left| \frac{F/R_g}{F/R_n} \right| = \left| \frac{R_n}{R_g} \right| = \left| \frac{k_g}{k_n} \right| \quad (3)$$

where k_n and k_g represent the normal and geodesic curvature (dimension: 1 / length unit) respectively, and μ stands for the coefficient of friction. In the case of applying geodesic trajectories, the geodesic curvature becomes equal to zero; this immediately leads to the conclusion that geodesic fibre paths do not require any friction between mandrel and roving.

The calculation procedure for the geodesic curvature is outlined in the next subsection. For a given winding angle on a shell of revolution (figure 2), the normal curvature can be obtained by combining the meridional (k_m) with parallel curvature (k_p) according to [2, 5, 7]:

$$k_n = k_m \cos^2 \alpha + k_p \sin^2 \alpha \quad (4)$$

For a shell defined in a polar coordinate system ($\mathbf{S}(\rho, \phi) = \{\rho \cos \phi, \rho \sin \phi, z(\rho)\}$) the meridional and parallel curvature are respectively given by [2, 7]:

$$R_m(\rho) = \frac{1}{k_m(\rho)} = -\frac{(1 + z'(\rho)^2)^{3/2}}{z''(\rho)} \quad (5)$$

$$R_p(\rho) = \frac{1}{k_p(\rho)} = -\frac{\rho \sqrt{1 + z'(\rho)^2}}{z'(\rho)}$$

Development of the winding angle

Let a continuous three-dimensional curve on a regular surface be defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{C} : s \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3 : \mathbf{C}(s) = \mathbf{C}(\phi(s), \theta(s)) \quad (6)$$

The curve has an orientation $\alpha(\theta)$ with respect to the meridian (figure 2). According to [2, 5, 7], the geodesic curvature is given by:

Fig. 2: Definition of the winding angle (curvatures included)

$$k_g(\theta) = -\frac{d\alpha(\theta)}{d\theta} \frac{\cos\alpha(\theta)}{\sqrt{G(\theta)}} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{E_\theta(\theta)}{E(\theta)} \frac{\sin\alpha(\theta)}{\sqrt{G(\theta)}} \quad (7)$$

where:

$$G = \left(\frac{\partial x}{\partial \theta}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial \theta}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial \theta}\right)^2 = \mathbf{S}_\theta \cdot \mathbf{S}_\theta \quad (8)$$

$$E = \left(\frac{\partial x}{\partial \phi}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial \phi}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial \phi}\right)^2 = \mathbf{S}_\phi \cdot \mathbf{S}_\phi$$

For simplicity we assume here that the shell under consideration is defined in polar coordinates ($\mathbf{S}(\rho, \phi) = \{\rho \cos \phi, \rho \sin \phi, z(\rho)\}$). Solving equation (7) for $d\alpha/d\rho$ and substituting equation (5) into the result, leads to:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{d\rho} = -\frac{\tan\alpha(\rho)}{\rho} \pm \mu \left(\frac{\sin\alpha(\rho) \tan\alpha(\rho) z'(\rho)}{\rho} + \cos\alpha(\rho) \frac{z''(\rho)}{1+z'^2(\rho)} \right) \quad (9)$$

which is a first order non-linear ordinary differential equation.

COMPOSITE PRESSURE VESSEL DESIGN

The effect of geodesic curvature

When the fibre band is placed on the mandrel according to non-geodesic trajectories, a lateral force will be required to keep that fibre band in place (figure 1). As outlined in the second section, an additional curvature in lateral direction will be present. Hence, by activating the stability constraint given in equation (3), the total curvature characterising the fibre path is given by:

$$k_t = \sqrt{k_n^2 + k_g^2} = k_n \sqrt{1 + \mu^2} \quad (10)$$

As derived in [3, 4, 6, 8], the ability of a shell to oppose internal pressure is generated by the presence of curvature. In the case of fibre bundle that is placed on a curved shell in a non-geodesic fashion, the equilibrium of forces is given by (see also figure 1):

$$F = F_{\text{normal}} + F_{\text{lateral}} = f(R_n + R_g) = fR_n \sqrt{1 + \mu^2} \quad (11)$$

where f is the force per unit of length acting perpendicular to the fibre (similar to f_n and f_μ , as depicted in figure 1). The effect of friction is an increase in fibre force, needed to counterpart f (which is directly coupled to the internal pressure of the vessel and therefore can be considered as a fixed parameter).

Shape equation

Fig. 3: Basic ring element belonging to a fibre reinforced vessel

An elementary ring is here considered, belonging to a composite pressure vessel (figure 3). The surface representing that vessel is assumed as defined in polar coordinates. The winding angle α is defined according figure 2.

The (curved) fibre elements must be in equilibrium with the force generated by the internal pressure that is acting on the ring surface (perpendicular to ds). The ring is overwound by n fibre bundles, where each of them generates a force f . The expression for the equilibrium of forces is [4]:

$$nfdl = 2P\pi\rho ds \Rightarrow \frac{nf}{\pi P} = 2\pi\rho \frac{ds}{dl} = 2\pi\rho \cos \alpha \quad (12)$$

In the last equality the left part ($nf / \pi P$) is now denoted by S . Substitution of equation (11) into (12) leads to:

$$S = \frac{2\rho}{k_t} \cos \alpha \quad (13)$$

The design of composite pressure vessels is traditionally based on geodesic trajectories. For this kind of fibre placement, the so-called Clairaut equation is valid [2–10]:

$$\sin \alpha = \frac{c}{\rho} \quad (14)$$

where c is the polar opening radius. In this case, the geodesic curvature becomes equal to zero, hence k_t should be replaced by k_n . By involving only the normal curvature, the classical solution is obtained where the lateral fibre force is equal to zero. Substitution of equation (14) into (13) followed by integration, leads to [3, 4, 6]:

$$z'(\rho) = \frac{K + \rho^2}{\sqrt{(K + \rho^2)^2 - S^2 \cos^2 \alpha(\rho)}} \quad (15)$$

where K is an integration constant that represents an eventual axial force A on the polar cap. The value of K is given by dividing this force A with the factor πP . We should note here that this equation is actually expressing the axial equilibrium of forces while assuming geodesic

fibre trajectories. The shape obtained from integration of (15) is here indicated here by the term “classical isotensoid profile”.

NON GEODESICS ON CLASSICAL ISOTENSOIDS

In the case of non-geodesic winding, the parameter α is undetermined and will strongly depend on the available friction and curvature distribution (equation (3)). Before proceeding to the evaluation of such vessels, some restrictions on the winding angle distribution must first be identified. Setting the square root argument of equation (15) equal to zero, leads to the following constraint for $\alpha(\rho)$ (see the dotted limiting curves in figures 4 and 5):

$$\alpha(\rho) \geq \arccos\left(\frac{K + \rho^2}{S}\right) \quad (16)$$

The value zero for the denominator of equation (15) is obtained at the equator (ρ_{eq}) and, by approximation, the polar opening of the vessel (c). At the equator, the following condition holds true:

$$S = \frac{K + \rho_{eq}^2}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{c}{\rho_{eq}}\right)^2}} \quad (17)$$

Recalling equation (9), for the satisfaction of condition (17) and the creation of C^1 continuity of the roving path when passing the equator, the winding angle derivative must have the same value as the derivative of a geodesic path (derivative of $\arcsin(1/\rho)$) at exactly that place. Therefore, the friction at that point should be equal to zero. For this reason we introduce the following friction distribution:

$$\mu(\rho) = m \frac{\rho_{eq} - \rho}{\rho_{eq} - \lambda c} \quad (18)$$

where m is the maximally available coefficient of friction and λ a constant influencing the slope of the linear friction distribution. With $z = Zc$, $\rho = Yc$, $\rho_{eq} = Y_{eq}c$ and $r = K / \rho_{eq}^2$, substitution of (15) and (18) into (9) gives:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dY}(Y_{eq}, r, \lambda, m, Y) = -\frac{C_1 + (C_2 + C_3) \tan \alpha(Y)}{Y(C_2 + C_3)} \quad (19)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} C_1 &= \frac{m(Y_{eq} - Y)(Y^2 + 2Y_{eq}^2) \cos \alpha(Y)}{Y_{eq} - \lambda} \\ C_2 &= \sqrt{-\left(Y^2 + rY_{eq}^2\right)^2 + \frac{Y_{eq}^4(1+r)^2 \cos^2 \alpha(Y)}{1 - \frac{1}{Y_{eq}^2}}} \\ C_3 &= \frac{m(Y_{eq} - Y)(Y^2 + 2Y_{eq}^2) \sin \alpha(Y)}{Y_{eq} - \lambda} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

At the same time, the minimum allowable value for the winding angle (17) becomes:

$$\alpha_{\min}(Y, r) = \arccos\left(\frac{Y^2 + rY_{eq}^2}{Y_{eq}^3(1+r)^2} \sqrt{Y_{eq}^2 - 1}\right) \quad (21)$$

With a given maximum coefficient of friction m and the friction distribution gradient parameter (λ), the winding angle $\alpha(Y)$ is given by the numerical solution of (19). The maximum fibre loading is given by substituting $\rho = \rho_0$ in equation (19). For $\lambda = 1$ the relative increase in fibre loading as compared to a geodesic vessel, is given by $\sqrt{m^2}$.

ISOTENSOIDS BASED ON NON-GEODESICS

The central assumption here is that for the placement of rovings on the mandrel, the constraint (3) is active. The goal is to design a meridian profile that will provide equal fibre tension everywhere, despite the presence of geodesic curvature. To achieve this goal, we substitute equation (4) into (10) and plug the result into equation (13). After some rearrangements, the second derivative of the meridian profile is given by:

$$\frac{d^2z}{d\rho^2} = -\frac{[1 + z'(\rho)^2][z'(\rho)S\sqrt{1 + \mu^2} \tan^2 \alpha + 2\rho^2 \sec \alpha \sqrt{1 + z'(\rho)^2}]}{S\sqrt{1 + \mu^2} \rho} \quad (22)$$

Plugging this expression in equation (9) and simplifying, results in:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{d\rho} = -\frac{\tan \alpha(\rho)}{\rho} - \frac{2\mu\rho\sqrt{1 + z'(\rho)^2}}{S\sqrt{1 + \mu^2}} \quad (23)$$

Simultaneous solution of the system of differential equations consisting of (22) and (23) will finally provide the shape and winding angle distribution along the coordinate ρ for the desired pressure vessel.

For the solution of the system ((22), (23)), the initial set of values consists of: $z'(c) = 0$, $z(c) = 11$ (arbitrary value) and $\alpha(c) = \pi/2$. In regard to the windability of the vessel, the winding angle at the polar areas should rapidly approach the value $\pi/2$. For the numerical solution of the system ((22), (23)) however, a slightly reduced initial value for α is rather desirable. The same idea applies on $z'(c)$ where the assumed slope should be given by a very small negative number.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Non-geodesics on classical isotenoids

To demonstrate the effect of non-geodesic trajectories on the resulting winding angle distribution on a geodesics-based meridian profile, we examined here two cases corresponding with $m = -0.2$ and $m = 0.2$. Furthermore, we assumed that $Y_{eq} = 10$, $r = 0$ and $\lambda = 1$.

Fig. 4: Winding angle development on an isotensoid profile by positive friction

Fig. 5: Winding angle development on an isotensoid profile by negative friction

As expected, the sign of the friction applied on the roving is accordingly influencing the winding angle distribution. Notice that the sign of the applied coefficient of friction is additionally influencing the polar opening radius, which can be increased or reduced. This principle sets the ability for controlling the polar opening radius.

Isotensoids based on non-geodesics

The system of equation (22) and (23) is here evaluated with the following conditions: $S = 100$ (typical range: [15-100]) and $\mu = 0.2$. In figure 6, a comparison between geodesic and non-geodesic winding is provided, in terms of winding angle development.

Fig. 6: Winding angle development for geodesic and maximum friction-utilising non-geodesic winding on an optimal pressure vessel

In the figure below, the difference between a geodesic and a maximum friction-based profile is depicted:

Fig. 6: Meridian profiles for geodesic and maximum friction-utilising non-geodesic winding

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this paper we have outlined the application of non-geodesic trajectories on isotenoid pressure vessels. After a brief presentation of the theory supporting the creation of non-geodesic trajectories, the basic equations providing optimal meridian profiles are highlighted. With the geodesics-based optimal meridian profile as a basis, we have evaluated the effect of friction on the fibre layer geometry and assessed the available design space. In addition, the maximum-friction-utilising non-geodesics -based optimal meridian profile is derived as well.

Although the shape differences in geodesics and non-geodesics-based meridian profiles are rather small, the available design space is sufficiently enlarged. This increase of possibilities particularly reflects on the radius of the polar opening that the fibre paths can reach, while still being able to reasonably oppose the forces generated by internal pressure.

An assumption of major importance here is that we consider dry tows, hence the required lateral forces are induced by friction. In the case of matrix application as well, the mechanical performance of the vessel will significantly drop since the lateral forces will now be generated by interlaminar shear stresses and in-plane compressive forces. Therefore it is strongly

recommended for the designer to thoroughly consider a trade-off between strength reduction and desired design space expansion in terms of flexibility for the minimum and maximum radius the aimed vessel should have.

REFERENCES

1. Beukers A, Hinte E van. *Lightness: The inevitable renaissance of minimum energy structures*. Amsterdam: 010 Publishers, 1998.
2. Gray A. *Modern Differential Geometry of Curves and Surfaces*. CRC press, 1993.
3. Jong de Th (in Dutch). “*Het wikkelen van drukvaten volgens de netting theorie*”. Report VTH-166. Structures and materials laboratory, Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, Delft University of Technology. Delft, April, 1971.
4. Jong de Th. *A theory of filament wound pressure vessels*. Report LR-379. Structures and materials laboratory, Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, Delft University of Technology. Delft, April, 1983.
5. Koussios S, Bergsma OK, Mitchell G. “Non-geodesic Filament Winding on Generic Shells of Revolution”. *Journal of Materials Part L: Design & Applications*. Submission date: May, 2003. Acceptance date: July 2004.
6. Koussios S, Bergsma OK. “Analysis of Filament Wound Pressure Vessels Considering the Laminate Thickness Variation through the Meridional Direction”. In: *Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Composite Materials*. San Diego, CA, July 2002.
7. Kreyszig E. *Mathematical Expositions Nr. 11: Differential Geometry*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 1959.
8. Vasiliev VV, Krikanov AA. “New generation of filament-wound composite pressure vessels for commercial applications”. *Composite Structures* 2003; 62: 449-459.
9. Wells GM, McAnulty KF. “Computer aided filament winding using non-geodesic trajectories”. In: *Proceedings of the second European Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM/ECCM)*. London, 1987; 1.161-1.173.
10. Xian-li Li, Dao-hai Lin. “Non-geodesic winding equations on a general surface of revolution”. In: *Proceedings of the second European and 6th International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM/ECCM)*. London, 1987; 1.152-1.160.